

Enhancing the Achievement of Subject-Verb Agreement Among the Year 5 Students Using Word Bricks Game

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to investigate the achievement of Subject-Verb Agreement among Malaysian students of year 5 using the Word Bricks Game and the students' perception towards learning Subject-Verb Agreement using Word Bricks Game. Subject-Verb Agreement is unavoidably necessary for mastering English language which is taught as a second language in Malaysia. Students who study English at a young age with simple and correct systems would be successful communicators in the future. Students can only interact efficiently in restricted circumstances if they do not learn Subject-Verb Agreement. Furthermore, Subject-Verb Agreement is regarded as a vital component of the study of language and ideas. Subject-Verb Agreement, in reality, aids humans in analysing and describing their words. Word Bricks Game was used to enhance the achievement of Subject-Verb Agreement since students who used games to learn felt more inspired and excited about their work. Qualitative research design is used in this study. The participants comprised of 40 students from a primary school in Kuala Lumpur. Observation and interview were used as the methods for data collection. Findings include the interview responses from the year 5 students and opinions shared by some English teachers, and researchers' observations of the learning process of Subject-Verb Agreement using Word Bricks Game. The findings showed that year 5 students have positive perceptions towards the learning of Subject-Verb Agreement using Word Bricks Game. They also have high-level of acquisition of Subject-Verb Agreement using Word Bricks Game in the learning process. In addition, English teachers shared their opinions on the important criteria of the games which should be considered before teaching Subject-Verb Agreement.

Keywords: *Achievement, Perception, Subject-Verb Agreement, Teaching English using Games, Word Bricks Game,*

Introduction

According to Kayan and Aydin (2020), previous studies have shown that students of today have negative attitudes toward conventional grammar teaching approaches and strategies, and that their academic results have fallen short of expectations. The failure of this process is related to the failure to use approaches and strategies that are consistent with the adopted educational theory.

As mentioned by Hong et al. (2021), the problem of English language proficiency among Malaysian students has long been a topic of debate among educators. Despite the fact that English is taught as a second language in primary and secondary schools, many students, especially those from rural areas, struggle to use it correctly. It has also been said that in most rural settings, students' English language proficiency takes a long time to develop. Furthermore, it has been suggested that in most rural contexts, English language learning is more a process of foreign language learning than second language learning. Shafizan (2020), a teacher who taught English in Kedah admitted that some rural students were concerned when they were told they would study Science and Maths in English. Their concern was that they did not consider English a second language, but rather a foreign language. In addition, Maharam (2016) mentioned that the level of English proficiency among Year One students from various faculties at Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia is still at a moderate level, with the average Malaysian University English Test band being band 2.

Students' academic performance has also been affected by the Covid-19 pandemic. According to the Radzi (2020), the Prime Minister Tan Sri Muhyiddin Yassin has instructed all schools, public, private, international and universities to be closed in line with the Movement Control Order (MCO) implemented by the Malaysian government. The Prime Minister said home-based learning was to be utilised during the MCO (Radzi, 2020). Thus, online learning methods are a necessity. Learning Subject-Verb Agreement (SVA) using Word Bricks Game (WBG) can be conducted via online learning, where digital WBG can be used effectively and create more interest in the process of learning among the year 5 students. There are few online learning platforms such as Blackboard, Edmodo and Google Classroom. One of the popular tools of online learning is using Google Classroom. Teaching SVA using WBG via Google Classroom can be implemented, where students can participate in the learning process using technology devices such as laptops, tablets, computers and smartphones. Google Classroom allows teachers to monitor their classrooms from anywhere and at any time. Teachers can have online classes or group classes for each lesson using Google Classroom. For both students and teachers, Google Classroom has made the learning process much simpler and more efficient. Google Classroom is a simple and user-friendly tool. It allows teachers and students to collaborate in a much more efficient manner, allowing teachers to focus on their planning while students can complete all of their Google Classroom homework (Muhammad Astrianto Setiadi, 2020).

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of this study is to investigate the achievement of SVA among year 5 students using WBG and the students' perception towards learning SVA using WBG.

The objectives of the researcher are as follows:

- i. To identify the extent to which year 5 students have good perception towards the achievement of SVA using WBG.
- ii. To identify the extent to which year 5 students have high-level of acquisition of SVA using WBG in the learning process.
- iii. To determine the important criteria of the games which should be considered before teaching SVA based on the teachers' opinion.

The research questions explored in this study are as follows:

- i. Do year 5 students have good perceptions towards the achievement of SVA using WBG?
- ii. Do year 5 students have high-level of acquisition of SVA using WBG in the learning process?
- iii. Based on the teachers' opinion, what are the important criteria of the games which should be considered for use in teaching SVA?

Literature Review

Teaching English Using Games

According to Nur Syafiqah and Melor (2019), the conventional teaching and learning method of chalk-and-talk has become obsolete. Teachers and students are introduced to a variety of task-based processes in order to increase student engagement in the class. The use of language games to aid the teaching of different skills is one of the most popular and favoured teaching strategies. Language games have evolved into a new and advanced forum for learners to participate in lessons as a result of the growth of interactive learning platforms and online applications being used in lessons. The use of interesting and appropriate resources, as well as a variety of approaches when conducting language games during lessons, aids in catering to learners' needs and interests on the subject matter, especially in learning languages.

Akdogan (2017) mentioned that games have great educational value and can be improved so that students use language instead of learning the correct formula. Besides, games help students to interact, collaborate and be creative in using language in a beneficial way. In order for students to participate in the game, they must be able to understand and communicate in English. In addition, games can encourage students to be interested in the learning process and be used as a method or technique to engage students in learning. Suitable games give students a break and help students practise their language skills. In addition, the game adds flexibility and fun, and involves friendly competition to keep students interested and motivated. Games encourage active learning, as well as collaboration and interactivity, providing memory, performance, and social benefits. As mentioned by Lin et al. (2020), in the field of English language teaching, the educational importance of interactive game-based language learning has piqued interest. Grammar is rarely discussed among all language-specific skills in game-based language learning, despite the fact that learning grammar is one of the most difficult areas to master for English as a Foreign Language (EFL) students.

Yolageldili and Arikan (2011) mentioned that games are important for English students and teachers because they provide fun and relaxation and encourage students to use their language creatively and communicatively. It is important to know that learning a language is a challenging task that requires constant effort, especially for young students. Games encourage students to generate their energy to learn the language by giving them meaningful knowledge. Therefore, it is important that teachers use games in their foreign

language teaching programs. Games involve many factors, including applying rules, encouraging collaboration, and fun learning. The game has a clear start and end and is governed by rules. Game-related competition plays an important role as required by the nature of the game. Students are excited to see who wins or loses and the outcome remain unanswered until the end of the game. The fun nature of games can encourage successful learning. To achieve the goal, players must work together and enjoy collaboration and social interaction. When collaboration and interaction are combined with fun, successful learning is achieved.

Sahar (2016) said that games are important and useful because they are fun and help students communicate and make predictions. Moreover, understanding the game helps the teachers assist their students learn to play. Hang (2017) mentioned nine key aspects of games which can be used for educational purposes.

- i. The games are student-centred.
- ii. The games help students develop communication skills.
- iii. The games help create meaningful contexts in which students can learn the language.
- iv. The games encourage students' learning.
- v. The games reduce students' fear of learning.
- vi. The games integrate the language skills of the students.
- vii. The games encourage the students' creativity and spontaneous use of language.
- viii. The games help develop a spirit of collaboration among students.
- ix. The games encourage the spirit of participation among the students.

Hang (2017) added that games are a type of tool which enhances students' attitude towards learning and develops their language skills. In addition, games need to be implemented and adapted to the learning process so that they can be used as an effective teaching tool.

According to Victoria (2017), playing games in the classroom has many benefits. Firstly, games can increase students' enthusiasm. Furthermore, playing in the classroom boosts overall motivation. Students are more likely to read, observe, and engage in assigned activities while they play. Students learn to work as a team and take responsibility for their own learning through games. They can also be useful classroom management tools for keeping students engaged. In the classroom, students, especially boys, can be fiercely competitive. In addition, games are the most effective way to manage peer competition. While playing, students will compete with one another. Many games necessitate problem-solving and strategic planning. Students may use their minds to solve problems and increase their mental awareness by using a variety of in-game techniques. Using in-game strategy to stimulate the brain can be extremely beneficial.

As stated by Victoria (2017), some students find answering questions on a spreadsheet or making a text page to be boring and stressful. This often contributes to a negative image of the student learner. Alternatively, games can be used as a tool that puts less stress on students in the learning process. Playing games can improve student memory as students need to remember the topic so that they can think and act quickly. In addition, playing in the classroom inspires a sense of teamwork. Students should work as a team while playing. Through games, students take turns learning, building respect, listening to others, and playing honestly. Also, playing games helps students pay attention since they need to be alert and attentive. Playing in the learning process is always enjoyable. Play in class to incorporate new knowledge. After teaching new content, teachers can offer students games that will strengthen their understanding and make connections with what they have learned. Nur Syafiqah and Melor (2019); Kayan and Aydin (2020); Lin et al. (2020) have conducted studies on the efficacy of using games in teaching the English language.

Word Bricks Game

The instructor gives the players five conditions for constructing their sentences in WBG. The first team to correctly complete all five patterns wins the game. On one brick, one word is typed. Potential trends include:

- i. 1 sentence of exactly 5 words - John goes to school today.
- ii. 1 sentence of exactly 6 words – Mary plays the piano at home
- iii. 1 sentence of exactly 7 words – Donny likes to eat watermelon very much.
- iv. 1 sentence of 2 verbs – Simon eats two bananas and drinks a glass of milk.
- v. 2 sentences of 2 different verbs – I am jumping. She is dancing.

Instructions:

- i. Ask students (players) to sit in pairs or small groups and choose the team name for their group. Each group receives an almost identical number of bricks.
- ii. On the board, make a space for each team and write the team name at the top. Make a list on the board showing the conditions for each round of the competition.
- iii. Tell the players that the game is a race and that the team must make grammatically correct sentences that exactly follow the conditions listed on the board. Follow each condition and explain that the team must complete the sentences in the order shown on the board.
- iv. Start the game and ask players to call you when they think they have the right phrase. If the phrase is grammatically correct, give the team a point and write it on the board.
- v. The first team to make a sentence according to each pattern can earn 5 points.

(Activate: Games for Learning American, n.d.)

Subject-Verb Agreement

According to Prasada and Martin (2019), in the context of present tense, a singular subject takes a singular verb, and a plural subject takes a plural verb. Below is a list of common SVA rules.

- i. Singular verbs end in –s or –es. For present-tense verbs, adding the –s makes it singular. If the verb is plural, there is no –s added.
Singular Verbs:
 - *The boy sleeps soundly.*
 - *The towel needs washing.*Plural Verbs:
 - *The girls sleep soundly.*
 - *The towels need washing.*
- ii. Compound subjects joined by "and" take a plural verb. A subject that is made up of two or more nouns is a compound subject. When the parts are connected by and, the subject is plural, so it takes a plural verb.
 - *The boy and the girl go to school.*
 - *Justin, Jezron and Jethro buy ice-cream.*
- iii. Subjects with singular nouns joined by 'or' or 'nor' take a singular verb.
 - *Either you or your brother watches the movie.*
 - *Neither the thunder nor the lightning frightens the dog.*
- iv. Subjects with a singular noun and a plural noun joined by 'or' or 'nor' take the verb that agrees with the closer noun.

- *Orange syrup or raisins taste good with oatmeal.*
- *Neither the boys nor their father goes to the market.*
- v. Subjects are not in modifying phrases. When the subject and the verb are separated by other words or phrases, make sure the verb agrees with the subject, not with a noun within the phrase.
 - *One of your buttons is missing.*
 - *Our neighbour, Mr Tan who grows oranges shares his harvest with us every year.*
 - *The citizens of Malaysia, vote today.*
- vi. Phrases using with, together with, including, accompanied by, in addition to, or as well as do not change whether a subject is singular or plural. If the subject is singular, the verb should be as well.
 - *The outfit, including the socks, costs \$45.*
 - *The twins, as well as their baby brother, ride in the shopping cart.*
- vii. Nouns with a plural form but with a singular meaning take singular verbs. Nouns such as United States, civics, mathematics, measles, and news take singular verbs.
 - *Mathematics is an interesting subject.*
 - *Twenty dollars is too expensive for a movie ticket.*
- viii. Nouns such as scissors, tweezers, trousers, jeans, and shears take plural verbs. These nouns may appear to have a singular meaning, but each of these things is made up of two parts.
 - *Jason's shorts look comfortable.*
 - *Her glasses make her look prettier.*
- ix. Collective nouns usually take singular verbs. A collective noun has a singular form even though it refers to a group of individuals or things. Examples include army, audience, crowd, group, team, committee, class, and family. These nouns take a singular verb when the group acts as one unit.
 - *The group follows the man.*
 - *The band plays classical music.*
 - *The team wins every race.*
- x. However, a plural verb is used when people or things within a group act separately. The team disagree about where to celebrate after the game. If the subject follows the verb, the subject and verb should still agree. When the normal subject-verb order is inverted in a sentence, the verb still agrees with the subject. For example, in sentences beginning with there or here, the subject follows the verb. Since neither there nor here is ever the subject of a sentence, the verb agrees with the noun that follows the verb.
 - *There is a frog on the floor.*
 - *Here are your clean shirts.*
- xi. With words that indicate portions, look to the object of the preposition. With words that indicate portions-percent, fraction, part, majority, some, all, none, remainder, and so forth-look at the object of the preposition (the noun following the of phrase) to determine whether to use a singular or plural verb. If the object of the preposition is singular, use a singular verb. If the object of the preposition is plural, use a plural verb.
 - *Two fifths of the candy bars are chocolate.*
 - *Twenty five percent of the students are clever.*
- xii. Be careful with indefinite pronouns. Indefinite pronouns do not replace a specific noun. The words each, each one, either, neither, everyone, everybody, anybody, anyone, nobody, somebody, someone, and no one are singular and require singular verbs. The words both, few, many, others, and several are plural and require plural verbs. The words all, any, more, most, none, and some may be either singular or plural depending on what the indefinite pronoun refers to.

- *Someone at the back of the classroom likes eating cake.*
- *Both girls have funny eyes.*

Perception

According to Savitra (2017) perception is the process by which each person organises and interprets the experiences of their senses in order to give meaning to their surroundings. As stated by William and William (2018), in humans, perception is the process by which sensory stimulation is converted into formal experience. The feeling is a function of both stimulus and the mechanism. One of the objectives in this study is to identify the extent to which year 5 students have good perception towards the achievement of SVA using WBG. The perception is the process by which year 5 students organise and interpret their experiences of using WBG in the acquisition of SVA. The relationship between students' perception of their learning environment using WBG and SVA importance will inspire them to learn more effectively. When perception influences are combined, it reveals students' attitudes about learning SVA and how much they have learned during the SVA learning process.

Methodology

The research design employed in this study was that of a post-intervention survey in which 40 students from a primary school in Kuala Lumpur participated. Observation and interview were used as the methods for data collection. Ten questions were prepared for the interview of year 5 students as follows:

- i. What is your opinion on WBG? Is the WBG interesting and helpful to you?
- ii. What is your opinion on friendly cooperative spirit among the participants during the lesson?
- iii. What is your view on participants helping one another during the lesson?
- iv. What is your opinion on the eagerness to learn SVA among the participants during the lesson?
- v. Can you give your opinion on the participants' active involvement in the WBG activities?
- vi. What is your view on the spirit of sharing knowledge among the participants during the lesson?
- vii. Why do you think WBG is very suitable in learning SVA?
- viii. How does WBG help you improve your SVA achievement?
- ix. What is your perception towards the lesson using WBG in learning SVA? Is it good or bad?
- x. What is your acquisition of SVA using WBG? Is it high-level, moderate-level or low-level of acquisition?

For observation protocol, the following aspects were observed: classroom environment, WBG delivery structure, implementation of WBG and, lastly, how the WBG and SVA concepts were presented and whether the presentation was understood by all year 5 students.

According to Gay et al. (2011), observation is the process by which a qualitative researcher obtains data by observing participants. It is an understanding of the environment that the participants are experiencing, without changing or manipulating it. In this study, the observer recorded the behaviour but did not participate in the class. An uninvolved observer is less likely to be emotionally connected to participants. Non-participatory observation can also be better if the researcher does not have the necessary training or experience to act as

a true participant, or if the observed group is too organised for the researcher to easily fit in. However, it may be more difficult for a non-participating observer to obtain reliable information about the opinions, attitudes, and emotional state of participants than for a participating observer.

According to Gay et al. (2011), field notes are essential for collection, recording, and compilation during research. They provide details about what the observer saw or heard on the spot during the study, as well as information about the researcher's personal reactions to findings, experience, and thoughts during observation sessions. Because of the need for clarity and detail, recordings should be made in the field whenever possible during observation. The researcher should take field notes after leaving the environment, but the recording should be made as soon as possible. This is because as the interval between observation and field notes increases, the likelihood of distorting the original observation also increases. Field notes are information that will be evaluated to provide an overview of the study environment and participants. They should be as lengthy, concise, and informative as possible. In this study, researcher collected details about what have been seen and heard as well as the information about own personal reactions to findings during observation sessions.

Interviews are intentional encounters in which one person receives information from another, according to Gay et al. (2011). Researchers may gather valuable data from interviews that they would not be able to get from observation alone. Interviews can reveal knowledge that is not readily apparent. Observation cannot tell you what happened in the past. Interview questions may be derived from observational data. Interviewing allows you to better explore relationships, interests, feelings, problems, and values than observation. Based on the ten questions, researcher conducted the interview among the year 5 students. Several sessions have been done to collect details about year 5 students' perception towards the learning process of SVA using WBG. Besides, researcher had conducted several short sessions to collect details about the important criteria of the games which should be considered for the use in teaching SVA based on teachers' opinions.

Ethical Considerations

Qualitative researchers face ethical dilemmas such as respecting privacy, establishing truthful and accessible relationships, and avoiding misrepresentations as a result of the relationship and intimacy formed between researchers and participants in qualitative studies (Connelly, 2014). In all research studies, the security of human subjects through the implementation of relevant ethical standards is critical. Because of the in-depth nature of the study method, ethical issues have a special resonance in qualitative research (Siti Roshaidai, 2018). In this study, the name of students and school are kept confidential. Observation protocol, observation field notes and interview content are definitely confidential and students who took part in the interviews gave informed consent.

Findings

Based on the observations, all students used Google Classroom to follow the SVA learning process were studying in a safe and comfortable atmosphere. Their learning environments were always convivial, collaborative, and productive. In addition, their accommodations were large and comfy. WBG delivering structure was well organized and it was completed within the time allocated. Lesson plans were well prepared and the implementation of WBG was carried out smoothly and successfully with the active participation from year 5 students. WBG and SVA concepts were very well-presented and all

year 5 students were able to understand the explanations. All year 5 students have good perception towards learning SVA using WBG as they seemed to enjoy the lessons.

Based on the observations and interviews, the findings showed that year 5 students have good perception towards using WBG in the learning process and they have high-level of acquisition of SVA using WBG. Therefore, WBG can help improve the achievement of SVA among the year 5 students. Besides, WBG can help students to construct simple sentences using SVA. In addition, WBG can help students to detect the problematic sentences in SVA.

The observations also suggest students' memories can be improved by playing games. Students are able to recall important information about a subject while playing a game, as well as use their working memory to think and act quickly. In the classroom, playing games improves class cohesion. Classroom games can be used to foster teamwork. When playing WBG, students work together as a team. Students learn how to take turns, respect others, listen to others, and play equally in this way. Students pay close attention to detail while playing games. Since games move quickly, students must be alert and attentive while playing. This level of concentration when playing a game will help students remain focused on other classroom activities during the day.

Do year 5 students have good perception towards the achievement of SVA using WBG?

Based on the Interviews among year 5 students, all of them agreed that WBG is very interesting and helpful to them. They agreed that a friendly and cooperative spirit exists among the participants during the lesson where they did not argue and fight among themselves when playing the WBG in class. Instead, they were cooperative and friendly with one another as they knew the aim was to construct correct sentences. Students helped each other, gave ideas, corrected mistakes, and discussed with one another in order to construct correct sentences. The researcher noticed a spirit of eagerness to learn among themselves during the lesson. They mentioned that every student participated actively in the WBG activities. They mentioned that no student in the class was selfish, was reluctant to share his or her knowledge during the lesson. They agreed that using WBG can enhance the learning of SVA effectively. They also agreed that WBG is very suitable to be implemented in the process of learning SVA. By using WBG, they had acquired the knowledge of SVA greatly and they really improved a lot in learning SVA. Talking about the perception towards using WBG in learning SVA, all students had positive good perceptions towards using WBG in the SVA learning process.

The observations indicate that year 5 students are more inspired to learn, pay attention, and engage in set activities when they played WBG. Students learned to work as part of a team and take responsibility for their own learning through games. Games can also be used as a classroom management method to help inspire a group of students. Boys, in particular, may become extremely competitive in the classroom. Games are an excellent way to keep peer competition in check. Students compete against each other when playing a game in the classroom, then help each other during other learning activities. Games necessitate problem-solving tactics and preparation. Students use their working memory to solve problems by using a variety of tactics in a game, which improves their mental cognition. Using tactics in a game to stimulate the brain can be a perfect brain exercise. Including games in a lesson as part of the teaching and learning process helps to build a fun atmosphere in the classroom, encouraging students to participate and foster a positive attitude toward learning. In the classroom, games can build a good memory and learning environment for students. Games can be used as a less stressful alternative to worksheets for students to demonstrate their experience, abilities, and understanding of learning SVA.

Do year 5 students have high-level of acquisition of SVA using WBG?

All students understood clearly the WBG and SVA concepts and they were able to construct correct sentences. They were able to speak and write correctly. All of them agreed that they have high-level of acquisition of SVA after playing the WBG during the lesson. Students use their prior experience, expertise, multiple talents, and skills to assist the teacher in presenting the new data by enabling them to practise the new knowledge alongside their existing knowledge. According to the students, games are a lot of fun, which help them learn better. Students' negative attitudes towards SVA learning, which they thought was difficult and tedious before the implementation of WBG, shifted dramatically to positive attitudes, with learning SVA using WBG being an exciting and enjoyable class to attend. WBG has motivated year 5 students to have high-level of acquisition of SVA.

The observations indicate that playing games in the classroom is always exciting. Endorphins are released during game play, which stimulate the brain and give students a euphoric feeling. Students in the classroom experience a high level of satisfaction and enthusiasm as a result of this euphoria, resulting in a positive learning atmosphere. Games are an excellent way to help students retain new information in the classroom. After the teacher introduces new material to the class, students can play a game to help them remember it and make correlations with what they already know. Therefore, WBG helps year 5 students to have high-level of acquisition of SVA.

The observations also led to the discovery that games are the most suitable learning activity for year 5 students because games are a natural part of their existence. Students cannot pay attention for longer period of time. When the SVA teaching and learning process takes a longer period of time in the classroom, students can become bored and tired. This can lead them to become disinterested and unmotivated. Teachers should keep in mind that students enjoy being physically active while studying. Students are imaginative and inventive, and they unconsciously learn and motivated.

The observations also revealed that students use their past experiences, expertise, and a variety of skills and abilities to help teachers communicate new information by allowing them to practise new knowledge alongside previous knowledge. Therefore, the best way to channel this ability in grammar instruction is through games. It can be seen that most of the students are able to construct grammatically correct sentences. Based on the observations and interviews, when games are used during lessons, teachers have the opportunity to help students acquire new knowledge effectively. The game chosen should not be too complicated. A simple game is good enough because it is generally more effective and it does not require students to understand a long list of rules. Besides, teachers are encouraged to praise and encourage students when they have accomplished the tasks successfully because students always like to be the centre of attention.

Based on the teachers' opinion, what are the important criteria of the games which should be considered before teaching SVA?

Based on the opinions of the English teachers, when giving guidance and instructions to students, the teachers suggest that a few words in the mother tongue would be the quickest way to communicate with them. More exposure to English is used at a later point, according to the teachers. The teachers agreed that demonstrations rather than lengthy descriptions are the best way to organise the game. The teachers believed that games are one of the most effective ways to help students learn SVA.

The points of view of the English teachers recommend that they should be careful when choosing a game if they want the game to be more interesting and fun. Teachers should choose which games to introduce during the lesson to enhance the teaching and

learning process. Teachers should also understand whether the games used are solely for the purpose of making the lesson more engaging and preventing students from being bored or whether they intend to review and practise certain parts of grammar or vocabulary in English lessons. As the teachers disclosed during the interview, when considering the value of the selected game in teaching SVA, teachers should use it to reinforce certain aspects of grammar in English. It is critical that games allow for social interaction and involvement. Students can learn more effectively when they are surrounded by their peers.

Based on the opinions given by the English teachers, each game should have a straightforward linguistic outcome. The game can be a listening game to encourage students to hear a new grammatical form in action over and over again, or it can be a speaking game to allow students to practise the grammar after it has been absorbed by listening. Speaking games range in difficulty from simple repetition in a fun environment to more imaginative sentence formation for revision or advanced practise after the fundamentals have been mastered. The teacher should guide the students through this progression so that the students are all comfortable with the game at hand. As a result, games become enjoyable rather than tedious. Another thing to keep an eye on with games is that they include a large number of students at the same time. On the other hand, games that create confusion in the classroom and make teachers unpopular with their colleagues due to excessive noise levels are on the other end of the spectrum.

Discussion

This study investigates the teaching and learning of SVA using WBG among the year 5 students. It draws a conclusion that WBG is an effective tool for learning SVA as WBG creates engagement, connection and in-context learning among the year 5 students. It also saves time as students are directly exposed to using SVA in context and develop fluency in creating sentences. Nur Syafiqah and Melor (2019) have conducted their study on using language games in teaching and learning and their findings showed that language games are helpful in teaching and learning grammar for ESL students. Their study is useful in demonstrating the value of language games as a teaching strategy for improving students' English grammar acquisition. Besides, Kayan and Aydin (2020) conducted a study on the effect of computer-assisted educational games on teaching grammar. The results revealed that this method of teaching grammar had a substantial impact on students' achievement and attitudes. In addition, Lin et al. (2020) conducted a study on facilitating EFL students' English grammar learning performance and behaviours using a contextual gaming approach. They mentioned that by placing the experimental group in a contextual game-based learning approach while the control group learned with a traditional technology-assisted English learning approach, the treatment was performed to test the efficacy and game learning habits of the proposed learning approach. The experimental group's contextual error rate was substantially lower than the control group.

Some suggestions to be considered:

- i. Suggestions to the teachers: This study found that the WBG can be used to improve the SVA mastery of students and to make students enjoy themselves during English lessons. Besides, students should be given more exercises and other games that can help them learn SVA. In addition, students should have more practices in constructing correct sentences with the help of teachers.
- ii. Suggestions to the school: The school can provide more reference books for teachers and students where students and teachers can refer to these books in their teaching and learning process. The school can have facilities for students to improve their English skills, such as a multimedia room as well as a language

- laboratory.
- iii. Future researchers should consider the following suggestions: Students' SVA mastery can be improved by using WBG. They can use other games from word 67 bricks game or they can use sentence race of WBG to help improve other aspects of English grammar. The use of WBG in this study is a good suggestion for future researchers to introduce new methodologies to change this treatment. Additionally, prospective researchers may conduct research involving the use of games to teach English among secondary school students or students at institutions of higher learning.

Conclusion

The results indicate that the researcher's expectations for SVA were met. It is true that teachers' primary motivation for using games in the classroom with young learners is instructional, rather than as a warm-up or filler activity. When teaching English to young learners, games are an important method. When selecting games for young learners, teachers should ensure that the games are primarily designed to achieve lesson goals, provide group work skills, provide an acceptable degree of versatility and adaptability, and, as a result, allow young learners to learn English language in a fun and engaging manner. The study can be used as solid evidence to persuade teachers who still use a traditional and serious teaching style to start thinking about and adapting their technique to one that better fits the characteristics of their young students so that their learning output improves. Positive attitudes toward games conducted in this study can be used to inspire and empower teachers to assume that language learning games are one of the best activities for children when teaching them a foreign language like English. Remember that teaching students through games necessitates extra work on the part of the teachers. Teachers must choose and schedule which game to use, as well as the length of time the game will be played.

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